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CHRONIC ALCOHOLISM AS ETIOLOGICAL FACTOR OF DENTAL EROSION

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Abstract: Consumption of alcohol is an integral part of everyday life. Low pH value of alcoholic beverages (e.g. the pH value of Heineken beer is 4, white wine 3.2-3.5 and red wine 3.5-4.0) has a direct impact on the demineralization of hard dental tissue. The resulting dental erosions are deepened under the influence of gastric hydrochloric acid which reaches the oral cavity through vomiting and regurgitation in cases of alcohol intoxication, also causing the loss of protective function of saliva due to xerostomia which appears as a side effect of this type of addiction. Each presence of generalized erosive changes in which the case history has not detected an etiologic factor must create suspicion of chronic alcoholism and thus, this type of defect could be considered a symptom and, as such, it could be used in the diagnosis of this addiction. Dental erosions are also followed by certain complications such as: tooth fractures, pulpitis, periodontitis, lowering of the vertical dimension of the bite, damaging of temporomandibular joint. Twenty-first century is the century of preventive dentistry, only in this case the preventive measures taken only by dentists are not sufficient; the prevention should be multidisciplinary and must include dentists, nutritionists, gastroenterologists and psychiatrists

Alcoholism is the most common addiction and after depression, it is a mental disorder that in most cases contributes to global disability⁽¹⁾. Prolonged intake of large amounts of alcohol in the body leads to the adaptation of organism to alcohol and functional, later even organic, changes in the central nervous system (CNS) which are phenomenologically manifested as an addiction syndrome or alcoholism⁽²⁾.

Alcohol is a legalized psychoactive substance (LPS) and its transport and trade are regulated by the law. Drinking of alcohol is a socially acceptable activity and, in some cultures, such as ours, it has been even favored to the level of obligatory ritual in many different situations⁽¹⁾. One-third of adults in Serbia (31.6%), according to the data from 2006, used to consume alcohol two to three times during the period of a 30-day research. Everyday consumption of alcoholic drinks in Serbia was registered in 3.4 % of population, whereas an average consumption of alcoholic drinks per person amounted to 7.4ml. The largest percent of people who drink alcohol is between 20 and 34 years of age. Drinking amongst the young has a competitive pattern, i.e. they compete in who can drink more. Lately, combining various types of alcoholic drinks has become increasingly popular. A high-risk group for the development of long-term diseases and conditions resulting from the abuse of alcohol included a significantly larger percent of men (5.7%), whereas women were less affected (0.4%)⁽¹⁾. Excessive intake of alcohol represents one of the leading risk factors for human health in the world, due to the fact that the etiological factor causes more than 60 diseases and damages and it can also lead to death outcome in approximately 2.5 million people every year⁽³⁾.

Alcohol addiction has serious consequences on human health as it leads to the diseases of gastrointestinal tract⁽⁴⁾, central nervous system⁽⁵⁾, cardiovascular system⁽⁶⁾, skin⁽⁷⁾, respiratory⁽⁸⁾ and reproductive system⁽⁹⁾. Alcohol addiction damages the health of the whole organism and thus, all constituents of oral cavity. Salivary glands, especially parotid gland, could be enlarged in cases of chronic alcoholism, which is the consequence of peripheral neuropathy caused by ethanol⁽¹⁰⁾. Reduction of the salivary secretion leads to the reduction of saliva buffer capacity which, in combination with poor oral hygiene, causes changes of hard dental tissues as well as periodontal tissues. Alcohol addicts have a high risk of dental caries ⁽¹¹⁾, high incidence of caries, filled and extracted teeth ^(12,13), gingival-periodontal disease^(13,14), tongue inflammation, oropharyngeal cancer⁽¹⁵⁾ (especially if combined with the consumption of cigarettes). Except for carious changes, dental erosions ⁽¹⁶⁾ may also occur on hard dental tissues.

Chronic alcoholism is associated with high prevalence of dental erosions which is the consequence of *direct* acid effect of beverages (having a pH value of: Heineken beer 4.1; white wine 3.2-3.5; red wine 3.5-4.0)^(17,18), taking into consideration that the acidity of alcoholic beverages (pH value) is lower than the critical value for the demineralization of hard dental tissues (pH 5.5)⁽¹⁹⁾ or *indirect*, as a result of the appearance of gastric hydrochloric acid in the oral cavity due to chronic gastric regurgitation and vomiting provoked by alcoholic intoxication with the loss of protective functions of saliva due to the occurrence of xerostomia which is typical of this kind of addiction^(20,21,22).

Dental erosions

Dental erosion is defined as an irreversible loss of hard dental tissue caused by a chemical decomposition due to acids that are not of bacterial origin ^(23,16). In 1989 Smith BG. and Robb ND registered the existence of erosive changes in 92% of the examined teeth of alcoholics. The changes are more common in those who frequently consume alcoholic beverages compared to those who consume them occasionally ⁽²⁴⁾. Many *in vivo* as well as *in vitro* studies emphasize the relationship between the acidic drinks and dental erosions ^(25,26). Acids commonly present in beverages are as follows: citric, malic, tartaric, phosphoric and coal ⁽²⁷⁾.

There are two important factors that can affect the erosive potential of a solution: a low degree of saturation in relation to hydroxyapatite (fluorapatite) and the presence of acid or citrate, a substance capable of chelating the calcium of the teeth. There are several factors that are involved in the development of dental erosion: *intrinsic factors*, such as salivary flow rate, buffering capacity and salivary composition, pellicle formation, tooth composition; *extrinsic factors*, such as chemical (pH, titratable acidity, calcium and phosphate concentration, fluoride content of the material in contact with the tooth) and *behavioral factors* (eating and drinking habits, lifestyle, excessive consumption of acids)^(16,27-29). Ethanol ingestion affects the hypothalamo-neurohypophysial system resulting in increased diuresis, dehydration and hyperosmolality⁽³⁰⁾. Alcohol acts as a diuretic, which can lead to drying of the mouth. Some habits associated with drinking expand their deleterious effect on the enamel and can increase tooth erosion because they cause xerostomi. Such habits include smoking, drug abuse etc ⁽³¹⁾.

Low pH and the contact time between the acidic beverage and dental surface, play a crucial role in determining tooth wear. The pH of most alcoholic beverages is acidic, with values around pH 4.0 (lower than

the critical dissolution enamel pH 5.5) and the concentration of organic and inorganic acids is high. It is important that the pH of incomplete fermented drinks, such as beer and wine, is acidic because it helps prevent contamination by other microorganisms, while nowadays, the erosive potential is increased due to the combination of primary alcoholic beverages and soft drinks or fruit juices^(28,32,33). The potential of wines to cause erosion results from their fruit acid content, of which tartaric acid is the most abundant one. Different wines have different combinations and concentrations of acid types and other inhibiting factors present and thus, the erosive potential varies. For tooth crowns, there appeared to be little difference in depths of erosion resulting from the exposure to white wine or champagne-style wine, both at room temperature and at 37⁰C. The erosion resulting from red wine contact was substantially less than the one from both white wines. Riesling-style wine is more erosive than champagne-style wine and both are more erosive than claret⁽³⁴⁾. Amongst primary drinks, white wines are more erosive than red wines because of their higher concentration of titratable acids⁽³⁵⁾, while beer⁽³⁶⁾ and ciders⁽³⁷⁾ have a moderate erosive potential. Nogueira et al.(2000) evaluated the effect of different beer brands in relation to titratable acidity, calcium and phosphate concentrations and pH measurements, and observed that beer may have a potential dental effect, indicating calcium loss from the enamel over time⁽³⁸⁾. During fermentation in brewing, yeast is placed in the mixture and free amino acids are absorbed. Also, during fermentation, yeast is responsible for changing the buffer ability of beer, consumption of bases and acids excretion, increasing the amount of free hydrogen ions in the mixture responsible for pH reduction⁽³⁹⁾.

The astringency of alcoholic beverages is likely to be another factor promoting tooth wear- dental erosions. The taste typical of some alcoholic beverages is due to the presence of high levels of polyphenols, mostly tannins, which bind salivary proteins, such as proteins and mucopolysaccharides, causing their precipitation, with consequent sensation of astringency, losses of lubrication of the oral mucosa and teeth and simultaneous decrease in protection of teeth from acids⁽⁴⁰⁾.

Patophysiology and Pathohystology of dental erosion

Alcoholic patients are a risk group for dental erosion injuries, because alcohol consumption has the potential for degradation rate mechanisms. The mineral in our teeth is composed of calcium-deficient carbonated hydroxyapatite. These substitutions in mineral crystal lattice, especially carbonate, render tooth mineral more acid-soluble than hydroxyapatite. During the erosion caused by acids and/or chelators, these agents interact with surfaces of mineral crystals, but only after they diffuse through the plaque, the pellicle, and the protein/lipid coating of the individual crystals themselves. The effect of direct attack by the hydrogen ion is to combine with the carbonate and/or phosphate releasing all of the ions from the region of the crystal surface leading to direct surface etching⁽⁴¹⁾.

First, the prism sheath area and then the prism core on the enamel surface get dissolved, leaving a honeycomb appearance. Figure 1. Then, fresh and unionized acids diffuse into the interprismatic areas of enamel and further dissolve the mineral content underneath the surface. This acid attack leads to an outflow of ions and an increase in the pH in the surrounding environment⁽⁴²⁾. Loss of enamel leads to the opening of dentine tubules and a consecutive phenomenon of dentine hypersensitivity as one of the symptoms⁽⁴³⁾. The

pain is manifested as a shooting sensation to physical, chemical, thermal and evaporative triggers⁽²⁹⁾. The effects of acids on dentin have been largely investigated, as the length of time that teeth remain in the mouth is increasing, with dentinal coronal and root exposures that are gradually becoming common because of tooth wear and gingival recession, respectively⁽⁴⁴⁾. However, due to the high organic content of dentine, diffusion of demineralizing agents and mineral ions are partially stopped by the organic matrix, which acts as a barrier to acid diffusion and mineral release. Figure 2. This difference in erosive processes between enamel and dentine does not mean that the erosive process in dentine is slower, on the contrary, the dentine substrate is more susceptible to acid dissolution because its hydroxyapatite crystals are smaller than that of enamel^(45,46).

Figure 1. Scanning electron micrography of longitudinal cross-section of enamel 15 minutes after the exposure to filtrate of gastric juice

Figure 2. Scanning electron micrography of dentin roof of the pulp chamber after 15 minutes of exposure to filtrate gastric juice

Distribution and morphology of dental erosion in alcoholic

High consumption of alcoholic beverages and the problems associated with it: as a result of this, some dental surfaces are more affected by erosion in alcoholic patients. Alcohol –dependent patients undergoing an addiction rehabilitation therapy presented high experience and low severity of dental erosion lesions. Palatine surfaces of maxillary teeth, followed by occlusal surfaces of posterior teeth and incisal edges of anterior teeth, in average, were the more severe dental surfaces affected by erosion wear. Image 3. In these patients, the mandibular teeth and maxillary teeth buccal surfaces were the less affected by erosion wear (47). The primary signs of dental erosion are diminishing enamel luster, absence of macroscopic plaque and dental surfaces that have become rounded and polished because of the loss of micro anatomy. After the initial dental erosion, some features can be observed, such as smoothing out of developmental pits and grooves, dentin exposure, prominent restorations that are elevated above the surrounding tooth structure and well defined concavities of dentin on the occlusal and incisal surface, especially on the cusp tips of the posterior teeth. In more advanced cases, extensive mineral loss can lead to tooth shortening, which can promote functional and aesthetic problems. Convex teeth areas as proximal ridges gradually become flat and even concave. Image 4. In severe cases, dental morphology can be totally lost (48). Several epidemiological studies report a time-dependent association between chronic alcoholism and dental erosion, independently of socioeconomic status (28).

Image 3. Erosive changes on the oral surfaces of upper anterior teeth in a patient with gastroesophageal reflux disease

Image 4. Erosive changes in the teeth of the lower jaw in a patient with gastroesophageal reflux disease

Repeated or prolonged exposure of teeth to acid leads to selective dissolution of specific components of the tooth surface, with eventual loss of tooth substance, hypersensitivity, functional impairment, and even tooth fracture⁽⁴⁹⁾ and when excessive wear occurs possible complications are pain, pulpal inflammation, necrosis and periapical pathology⁽¹⁶⁾

From the dentists point of view a prerequisite for preventive measures is to diagnose erosive tooth wear and to evaluate the different etiological factors in order to identify persons at risk. No diagnostic device is available for the assessment of erosive defects. They can only be detected clinically. Initial evaluation begins with a thorough medical history review, with detection of repeated presence of gastric juice in the mouth (recurrent vomiting disorders or reflux or regurgitation) including a listing of all prescription and non-prescription medications and supplements and alcohol abuse. Items that are relevant to the problem of erosion include medications that may cause salivary hypo function and those used to treat GERD. Acidic medications or supplements such as Vitamin C and the method of ingestion should be noted. Through the process of risk assessment, the diet and the dietary factors predisposing the patient to the risk of dental erosion will be identified ⁽¹⁶⁾Dental professionals are urged to be aware of each patient's substance use history. It is therefore suggested that general dental practitioners should bear in mind the possibility of chronic alcoholism in cases of unexplained dental erosion. During the dental appointment, the health questionnaire and subsequent verbal interview should pose the relevant questions, allowing a patient to indicate a previous or existing alcohol abusing problem. Routine screening of patients for alcohol use and abuse, would allow dentists to detect patients most at risk and plan treatment and patient counseling accordingly.

A modern preventive strategy needs training of dentists in early detection and monitoring of the process because dental professionals are responsible for identifying early signs of dental erosion and implementing appropriate management strategies, including education and counseling. Also, a dentist has to provide a way of discussing alcohol with the patient and supporting behavior change through a health behavior change approach (change behaviors such as smoking, alcohol consumption, diet and physical activity)⁽⁵⁰⁾. Often patients themselves do not seek treatment until the condition is at an advanced stage or when the teeth become hypersensitive or when the aesthetics are affected.

Individually tailored advice for patients.

Alcohol abuse treatment should not only be focused on the medical and psychological management of the patient, but it also needs to include oral and dental treatment that may be necessary. Patients should be given advice on simple, practical ways to reduce the risk of erosive tooth wear such as dietary advice, modifying habits, remineralisation of dental defects, maintaining proper oral hygiene, professional application of fluoride and the application of occlusal guard.

Dietary advice: refers to the limited intake of acidic foods and beverages that are entered only during meals. We recommend the use of natural water in large quantities (8-10 glasses per day) and tea from calendula and

linden. The meal should be finished with milk or milk products containing 1.5% of fat. Other nutrition advice should be provided by nutritionists. In order for the reduction of reflux symptoms to occur, the following must be respected:

Modifying lifestyle: (to be emphasized to people with reflux symptoms)

- Dinner should be eaten 3 hours before going to bed;
- Avoid a horizontal position in bed, immediately after a meal;
- Sleep on an elevated headboard;
- Straighten your body when sitting or walking;
- Avoid voluminous meals;
- Avoid fatty foods, chocolate, coffee, peppermint, spicy foods, citrus ,tomato;
- Avoid alcohol and smoking;
- Regulate body weight;
- Eliminate excessive intake of analgesics, aspirin, ibuprofen, drugs against osteoporosis;
- Carbonated soft drinks consumed using a straw;
- Acidic drinks, alcoholic and non-alcoholic should be drunk at once, without sipping;
- Rinse your mouth with water after intake of carbonated beverages, wine and beer;
- Drink cold rather than warm beverages (if acidic)⁽⁵¹⁻⁵⁴⁾.

Remineralization of dental defects (individual recommendations)

- After vomiting or regurgitation rinse mouth with plain water⁽⁵⁵⁾ or
- Rinse with sodium bicarbonate (1ts in 250 ml water)⁽⁵⁶⁾ ;
- Once a day rinse your mouth with green tea⁽⁵⁷⁾;
- Between the acid attack rinse mouth with chlorhexidyne⁽⁵⁶⁾;
- Strengthen salivation with sugarless chewing gum with xylitol⁽⁵⁸⁾;
- Wash your mouth with fluoride 200-300pp once a day or
- Use fluoride tablets or lozenges⁽⁵⁴⁾.

Oral hygiene advice:

- Brush your teeth twice a day for two minutes⁽⁵⁹⁾;
- Use toothpaste with fluoride or with CPP-ACP (casein phosphor peptide - amorphous calcium phosphate) with low abrasiveness;
- Apply a soft or medium toothbrush;
- A toothbrush should be changed every three months;
- After vomiting brush your tongue;
- Check up every six months⁽⁵⁴⁾.

Professional application of fluoride :

- Periodically, in moderate high or high risk;
- The 2% solution of sodium fluoride (2-4 applications per year at high risk and 1-2 for moderate risk)
- 8-10% stannous fluoride (solution or jelly)

Application of protective appliance

- Application of occlusal guard during sleep, swim in the pool or provoke vomiting;
- Alkaline substances placed into the guard (Magnesium milk or neutral fluoride gels -5 min./24 hours with 1.1% neutral fluoride gel)^(54,55).

The twenty-first century is proclaimed a century of preventive dentistry. World Dental Association, World Health Organization and International Association for Research in Dentistry have brought the general and specific objectives for the provision of oral health to be achieved by 2020. Some of the general objectives are: to reduce the impact of general (systemic) disease on oral health, use already manifested symptoms (oral or craniofacial) for early prevention, focus on diagnosis and the effective treatment of systemic diseases. Serbia needs to improve preventive strategy through health promotion and good primary prevention. It is fundamental to note that without a valid multidisciplinary prevention there is no normal functioning of the stomatognathic system and protection of hard dental tissue in patients diagnosed with chronic disease⁽⁵⁴⁾.

As a healthcare practitioner, a dentist can play an important role in empowering individuals and communities to recognize how the alcoholic can improve their own health and well-being by informing patients of their health risk factors, and supporting them towards healthier options.

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